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1. Executive Summary

This report documents the GUTTA project financial progress during the reporting period ranging from 2019-01-01 to 2019-06-30, also termed in the following RP1. Please note that full reporting information is declared on SIU and the present report just represents an overview of its key contents. Moreover, the report does not take into account possible modifications to the present conditions, which may rise during the work of the FLCs.

When not re-defined here, shortcuts refer to the public GUTTA Glossary, which is found at: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1dm0XOR3_OrbRIJCE33XfEq2asu6QxqAx/view?usp=sharing

2. Project progress

The report is organized into General achievements (Sect.2.1), and Unforeseen Issues (Sect.2.2).

2.1 General achievements

Expenditures for RP1 were regularly reported by CMCC, CSA and UniZd in SIU, in consideration of the main activities performed during the period. Costs were incurred in all budget lines.

With respect to the AF financial planning, expenditures are occurring in a regular manner, with the exception of PP4 MMPI and PP5 AdSP, which did not report any costs in this RP1.

The overall financial progress, both at WP and budget line levels, is summarized in Fig.1-2.

Teleconferences (on 2019-05-23 and 2019-06-18) were organized for facilitating and checking financial implementation of the project among partners. Email exchanges were performed with partners and MA in order to solve financial reporting issues, e.g. expenditures occurred outside the programme area and small adjustments of partners budget.

Figure 1: Financial implementation status of GUTTA WPs. WP5 did not start in this RP and WP4 started in advance with respect to AF timeline. Blue is the implemented portion of the budget; orange is the missing portion within the current RP, and grey is the remaining portion until the end of the project.

Figure 2: Financial implementation status of GUTTA budget lines. Blue is the implemented portion of the budget; orange is the missing portion within the current RP, and grey is the remaining portion until the end of the project.

2.2 Unforeseen issues

2.2.1 CSA

-Minor budget amendments were requested (some travels outside programme area approved by MA).

2.2.2 UniZd

-Ship simulator seems to be crucial for implementation but budget is not sufficient. Budget amendments were requested for covering part of the costs of the simulator.

2.2.3 MMPI

-Reported no expenses in RP1, despite activities were reported.

2.2.4 AdSP

-Reported no expenses in RP1

3. Conclusions

The financial reporting of RP1 was not adequate mainly due to the missing financial reporting from partners MMPI and AdSP.

Therefore, pending issues during RP2 include:

- a) Recover of costs not declared in RP1 by MMPI;
- b) Recover of costs not declared in RP1 by AdSP, after appointing of a FLC.

These points will be also addressed during the next Steering Committee meeting, planned for Oct.2., 2019 in Zagreb (Croatia).